

striking case is seen for example, by electrolysis of a one per cent solution of acetic acid in a U-tube (25 mm diam, 30 cm high) sending 40 mA current (about 200 volts are necessary). We have electrolysed over a month and have observed no diminution of current. This means that though the solution contains about 4 milliequivalents of acetic acid, even over 1000 milliequivalents (i.e. 1 Faraday) of electricity fail to make the acetate ions migrate substantially to the anode. This is undoubtedly a striking behaviour and is apparently against the simple theoretical expectation.

Palit^{1,2} reported that electrolysis of dilute solutions of many electrolytes is attended with co-liberation, i.e. the cathode gas as well as the anode gas is an explosive mixture of hydrogen and oxygen. Since the actual ion concentration in such solutions is quite low, we naturally investigated this aspect. It has been found that considerable co-liberation takes place in such systems. At temperatures above 50° the cathode gas as well as the anode gas is a highly explosive mixture of hydrogen and oxygen only in a consistent manner even when the current is as high as 40 mA. Acetic acid solutions thus appear to be one of the few electrolytes which undergo non-Faradaic electrolysis even at high current density.

Theory: We first thought that this anomalous observation (constancy of current) is caused by the protonation of acetic acid ($\text{CH}_3\text{COOH} + \text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{CH}_3\text{COOH}_2^+$) and the consequent cathodic migration of the protonated species. Unfortunately however all our efforts to prove the existence of $\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}_2^+$ by direct migration experiments failed. We now believe that this is somehow connected with stationary boundary formation on electrolysis as reported by one of the authors³. In the present case we have found that the cathode solution becomes about 20 per cent weaker than the anode solution on electrolysis for a couple of days or so, and this equilibrium value remains practically unchanged thereafter however prolonged is the electrolysis. It is clear that a boundary forms between these two solutions and this boundary is of the stationary type¹ and this stationary boundary formation is somehow the cause of such stoppage of the acetate ion migration. This is consistent with our previous observation that once such boundary is formed, the current is practically exclusively carried by H^+ and OH^- ions, none other ions making any perceptible movement. It is however not clear why such a thing would at all take place; that is, why all other ions would stop migrating across a boundary with a sharp discontinuity in pH and consequent sudden change of potential gradient. However, this is an observed fact though an explanation has yet to be found out.

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References

1. S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 636.
2. S. R. PALIT, *Chemistry (Amer. Chem. Soc.)*, 1975, 48(5), 16.
3. S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 963.

Determination of Equivalent Weights of Acids, Alcohols and Amines by Titrating their Thiuronates with Sodium Methoxide

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A CIDS, some of the amines and alcohols can be characterized as benzylthiuronium carboxylates¹, benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates² and S-(2-benzoxoethyl) thiuronium xanthates³ respectively. These thiuronates can be titrated with sodium methoxide using thymol blue as indicator. As such, the procedure can be used for the determination of equivalent weights of these three classes of compounds. The procedures which are generally accepted for this purpose are: acidimetric titration of benzylthiuronium carboxylates⁴, picrates⁵ of amines and potassium xanthates⁶ in anhydrous acetic acid with perchloric acid using either visual or potentiometric indication. As a further check on the results, the equivalent weights may be determined by the procedure described below. Though tested with a select list of compounds, the procedure seems to be applicable to others as well.

Procedure—A thiuronate (100 to 200 mg.), prepared and purified according to the reported procedure, is dissolved in minimum volume of methanol followed by the addition of three parts of benzene. More benzene-methanol (3:1, V/V) is added if the solution is cloudy. Thymol blue (2 drops, 0.3% solution in methanol) is introduced and the solution is titrated against 0.1N sodium methoxide⁷ to a distinct blue colour in the case of salts of acids and alcohols, and brown colour in the case of those of amines. The end point is stable indefinitely in the case of acids whereas it is so for three minutes in the case of alcohols and one minute in the case of amines. Equivalent weights of chloroacetic acid, butyric acid, benzoic acid, *p*-chlorobenzoic acid, salicylic acid; dimethylamine, piperidine, phenylhydrazine, aniline, *O*-toluidine; methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, and *n*-butanol were determined. Maximum deviation in the results (average of three values) was found to be -0.24 to +0.24, -0.13 to +0.19 and -0.13 to +0.18 for acids, amines and alcohols respectively.

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References

1. F. G. MANN and B. C. SAUNDERS, "Practical Organic Chemistry", The English Language Book Society, IV Ed., 1974, p. 349.
2. N. N. SINGH and K. S. BOPARAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 1143.
3. N. N. SINGH and K. S. BOPARAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 1193.
4. J. BERGER, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, 8, 429.
5. J. R. CLARK and S. M. WANG, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 1230.
6. J. BERGER, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, 6, 1564.
7. J. KUCHARSKY and L. SAFARIK, "Titrations in non-aqueous Solvents", Elsevier Publishing Company, Amsterdam, 1965, p. 99.

Further Studies on the Structure and Stereochemistry of Entagenic acid

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EARLIER the structure of entagenic acid, a new sapogenin isolated from the seeds of *entada phaseoloides* Merrill (Syn. *E. scandens*, *E. pурсае-tha*), was proposed as 3 β , 21 α , 22 α -trihydroxy olean-12-ene-28-oic acid¹⁻³. Later in a short communication⁴ a revised structure, 3 β , 15 α , 16 α -trihydroxy olean-12-ene-28-oic acid (Ia), was proposed. Recently Wen Chin Lin *et al.*⁵ have isolated a glycoside of entagenic acid from *E. phaseoloides* which has been shown to have significant antitumour activity against 256 carcinoma in rats. The present paper describes further work which confirms structure (Ia) for entagenic acid.

It has been shown earlier⁴ that methyl entagenate on acetylation at 0° yields mainly diacetyl methyl entagenate and 3-acetyl methyl entagenate. A very small amount of triacetyl methyl entagenate is also formed. The diacetyl methyl entagenate was considered earlier to be a 3, 15-diacetate (Ib).

It was thought that if the diacetate was a 3,15-diacetate (Ib) then on dehydration by treatment with POCl₃ in pyridine on steam bath, it would lead to the formation of a 15-keto compound (II) as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

With this objective the above reaction was carried out. On working up a major product, C₂₉H₅₀O₅ (M⁺ 526), m.p. 192°, and another product in traces, C₂₉H₅₀O₅ (M⁺ 526), m.p. 203°, were obtained. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern (see Scheme 2) of the former (m.p. 192°) is typical of a 15-keto compound⁶ and hence the structure of the compound must be (II). If the keto group was not at 15 then instead of a peak at m/e 277 a peak at m/e 276 would have been observed due to normal r-D.A. fragmentation.

Scheme-2

The formation of the 15-keto compound (II) clearly locates the α -glycol system in entagenic acid at 15,